

**“OMMAVIY MADANIYAT” TA’SIRIDAN HIMOYALANISHDA INNOVATSION
USULLARIDA FOYDALANISH.****Rahmonova Sanoat Shuhrat qizi**

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti Tarix va filologiyakafedrasida o‘qituvchisi.

rahmonovasanoatshuhratqizi@oxu.uz<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15670519>

Annotatsiya. Madaniyat inson faoliyatining ichki mazmunini tashkil etadi. Shu nuqtai-nazardan qaraganda inson faoliyatining asosiy ma’no-mazmuni o‘zining erkin ijodkor shaxs sifatida ro‘yobga chiqarish, zarrama-zarra to‘plab insoniylik dunyosini yaratish va shu asosda olamni xam insoniylashtirishdan iborat. Shunday ekan, iste’molchilik kayfiyatining o‘zagini tashkil etgan “ommaviy madaniyat” haqiqiy madaniyatning mohiyatiga zid va yotdir. U insonni ma’nan majruh etadigan, uning ma’naviy dunyosini buzadigan, oxir-oqibat jon saqlashdan o‘zga maqsadi bo‘lmagan bir maxluq darajasiga tushurib qo‘yadigan, xalqni esa olomonga aylantiradigan hodisadir. Shuning uchun ham bunday madaniyatni “olomon madaniyati” deyiladi.

Kalit so‘z: “Ommaviy madaniyat”, globallashuv, Avesto, “ijtimoiy mavjudot” “madaniy mahsulotlar”, ma’naviyat, madaniyat.

Inson borki, atrofida yuz berayotgan voqelikka u yoki bu darajada munosabat bildiradi.

Aynan mana shu munosabat shaxsdagi ong, tafakkur, aql, bilim, qolaversa, tajribalarning mahsuli sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi. O‘z navbatida, inson omili har qachongidan ko‘ra, bugungi kunda muhim ahamiyat kasb etar ekan, uning bunyodkorlikka yo‘naltiruvchi kuchidan unumli foydalanish maqsadga muvofiq.

Millat taraqqiyoti haqida so‘z borganda qadimdan buyuk ajdodlarning intellektual salohiyati yuksalishida g‘oya muhim o‘rin tutgani ma’lum. Buni birgina bebaho ma’naviy xazinamiz “Avesto”ning tub mohiyatini belgilab beradigan “Ezgu fikr, ezgu so‘z, ezgu amal” g‘oyasidan ham bilsa bo‘ladi. Ayni paytda globallashuv jarayonida milliy g‘oya mafkuraviy ta’sir o‘tkazishning asosiy quroliga aylangan. Aytish joizki, “globallashuvning jadallashuvi sharoitida milliy ma’naviyat mavjudligining o‘zi yetarli emas, unda tashqi tahdidlarga qarshi qaratilgan ichki ruhiy qudrat, uning amal qilishi va faoliyat ko‘rsatishi ham zarur bo‘ladi” .

Rus olimi V.G.Fedotova, “ommaviy madaniyat” – “ildizsiz individlarni shakllantiradi” deb ta’kidlaydi, ommaviy axborot vositalari yordamida esa “ildizsiz”, zaminidan mahrum etilgan individlar ommasida paydo bo‘ladi. Bu bilan jamiyatda tartib-qoida va qadriyatlarni yuqotish (anomiya) holatiga tushadi. Yana bir rus olimi S.Naumov esa anomiya “individlarni jamiyatdan begonalashuviga olib boradigan tizim, jamiyatning normativ-funksional talablari bilan individlarning real xatti-harakatlari o‘rtasidagi bog‘lanishning buzilishi” – deb ta’riflaydi. Shunday qilib, globallashuv jarayoni va uning yo‘nalishlaridan biri bo‘lgan “ommaviy madaniyat” ekspansiyasi ta’siri natijasida sodir bo‘ladigan qadriyatlar tizimidagi tub o‘zgarishlar “ijtimoiy mavjudot” bo‘lgan insondagi o‘zgarishlarni keltirib chiqaradi. Buning xavotirli jihati shundaki, inson va jamiyat ma’naviy-axloqiy tayanchlaridan mahrum bo‘ladi, jamiyat inqirozga uchray boshlaydi.

Shu o‘rinda, “ommaviy madaniyat” tushunchasiga nisbatan salbiy qarashlar boisi nimada ekanligini tushunib yetmog‘imiz joizdir.

“Ommaviy madaniyat”ning qiyofasi quyidagicha:

1. U millati, yoshi, joyi, ijtimoiy xususiyatlarga bog‘liq bo‘lgan ommaviy iste’molchilarga ega bo‘ladi;

2. Bu madaniyat namunalarini yaratish jarayonining o‘zi ommaviy xususiyat kasb etib, industriyaning maxsus ko‘rinishini o‘zida namoyon qiladi, ya’ni unda yuz minglab kishilar band bo‘lib, ularning “matbuot qirol”, – shou tomoshabinlari, kino, TV, estrada yulduzlari bo‘ladi.

Ommaviy madaniyat kishilarni hayotni befarq kuzatuvchi tomoshabinga aylantiradi, o‘zlari ham mavjud hayotni go‘yo sarob kabi tasavvur qiladilar.

Ortega-i-Gasset ommaviy madaniyatning ta’sir doirasini tahlil etib, omma o‘ziga, shaxsga o‘xshamay qolishi, kimki boshqalarga o‘xshamasa, shulardek fikrlamasa tahlikada qolishini aytib, shunday degan edi: “Omna – yo‘riq-yo‘nalishsiz oqim bilan suzayotgan odamlardir.

Shuning uchun ular qobiliyat imkoniyatlari katta bo‘lishiga qaramay, hech narsa yaratmaydi. Ommaviy odam axloqdan mahrum, chunki uning mohiyati, ongi burchiga itoat qiladi”.

Ommaviy madaniyat umumiy iste’molchilar ehtiyoji bilan bog‘liq. Buning asosida iste’mol uchun talab, tovar sifatida haridorgir bo‘lish ehtiyoji yotadi. Oqibatda hozirgi zamon madaniyatidagi ma’naviy qadriyatlar tor doiradagi ehtiyojlarni qondirish vositasiga aylanadi.

Madaniyatning chuqur ma’no-mohiyati, xotira cheksizligi “kundalik”, “hammabop” xizmatlar bilan ijod avvaldan ma’lum, mavjud namuna asosidagi “asarlar” yaratish va ishlab chiqarish (kinoseriallar, sayoz TV va adabiy asarlar) bilan almashinadi. Shaxs o‘zining ijodiy qobiliyati, milliy ruhidan ayrilib, tayyor “madaniy mahsulotlar” iste’molchisiga aylanib qoladi.

“Ommaviy madaniyat” taqlidga andoza beradi (Reklamadagi chiroyli aktrisa kolbasani maqtab turadi...). Natijada uy bekasi unga taqlidan o‘sha kolbasadan oladi. Aktrisaning baxtiyor tabassumini eslab, o‘zini uning o‘rniga qo‘yadi. Unga o‘xshab tabassum qiladi. Kayfiyati ko‘tariladi. Chunki u (aktrisaning aytishicha), shirin, sifatli kolbasa sotib oldi. Ikkinchidan, (o‘sha aktrisa tasvirlagan) xushnudlikni tuydi. Shunday qilib, odam asta-sekin o‘zidan kechadi, “chiqadi”. Boshqa odamning dunyoqarashi, didi bilan ish ko‘ruvchi biomashinaga aylanib qoladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Yangi O‘zbekiston taraqqiyot strategiyasi asosida demokratik islohotlar yo‘lini qat’iy davom ettiramiz //“Xalq so‘zi” gazetasi, 2021 yil 7 noyabr, № 238
2. Ergashev I. Milliy istiqloq g‘oyasi: O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta’lim bakalavriat bosqichi uchun darslik. -T.: “Akademiya”, 2005, 93-b.
3. Rahmonova, S., & Turotova, S. (2025). O‘ZBEKISTONDA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN MA’NAVIY-MADANIY ISLOHOTLAR DINAMIKASI VA ASOSIY YO‘NALISHLARI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(5), 686–692. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/97354>
4. Rahmonova, S. (2025). YANGI O‘ZBEKISTONDA MA’NAVIY-MADANIY SOHADA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN ISLOHOTLAR. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(5), 1034–1040. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/91852>
5. Rahmonova, S. (2025). TA’LIM JARAYONIDAGI IJTIMOIIY-FALSAFIY YONDASHUVLAR. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 1046–1054. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/80463>

6. Rahmonova, S., & Turoпова, S. (2025). JADIDCHILIK FAOLIYATINING IJTIMOIIY-FALSAFIY AHAMIYATI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 397–403. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/81336>
7. Rahmonova, S. . (2025). IJTIMOIIY BEGONALASHUVNING OLDINI OLISHDA MA'NAVIY-MARIFIY ISLOHOTLARNING O'RNI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 428–435. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/60835>
8. Rahmonova, S., & Yo'ldasheva, M. (2025). TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 367–374. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/63683>
9. Rahmonova, S. (2025). MA'NAVIY TARBIYA YUKSAK MA'NAVIYATNI TARBIYALASH VOSITASI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 850–857. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/66726>
10. Rahmonova, S. (2024). SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL REFORMS ARE THE FOUNDATION OF A NEW UZBEKISTAN. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 517–525. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/58031>
11. Rahmonova Sanoat Shuhrat qizi. (2024). SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL REFORMS ARE THE FOUNDATION OF A NEW UZBEKISTAN. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14503228>
12. Rahmonova, S. (2023). DYNAMICS AND MAIN DIRECTIONS OF SPIRITUAL AND CULTURAL EFORMS IMPLEMENTED IN UZBEKISTAN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 850-854.
13. Rahmonova, S. (2023). YANGI O 'ZBEKISTONDA MA'NAVIY-MADANIY ISLOHOTLAR. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 2(10), 40-43.
14. Rahmonova, S. (2023). YUKSAK MA'NAVIYATLI AVLOD-UCHINCHI RENESSANS BUNYODKORLARI. *Наука и технология в современном мире*, 2(3), 76-79.
15. Rahmonova, S. (2024). THE REFORMS IMPLEMENTED IN NEW UZBEKISTAN ARE THE FOUNDATION OF THE THIRD RENAISSANCE. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 394-399.
16. Qizi, R. S. S., Shukhratovna, T. S., & Karamatovna, M. A. (2024). Implementation of Education and Protection of Children's Rights in the age of Technology. *SPAST Reports*, 1(7).
17. Рахмонова, С. (2024). HARMONY OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING. *Журнал универсальных научных исследований*, 2(5), 366-375.
18. Ramatov, J., Hasanov, M., & Rahmonova, S. (2024). TA'LIM TIZIMI MODERNIZATSIYALASHUVINING IJTIMOIIY-FALSAFIY ASOSLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 4(8), 160-172.
19. Rahmonova, S. S. Q. (2024). O'ZBEKISTONDA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN MA'NAVIY-MADANIY ISLOHOTLAR DINAMIKASI VA ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI. *International scientific journal of Biruni*, 3(2), 95-104.
20. Rahmonova, S. (2024). SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL REFORMS ARE THE FOUNDATION OF A NEW UZBEKISTAN. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 517–525. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/58031>

21. Xayrullayev , U., Sayfutdinov , F., & Rahmonova , S. (2025). SHAYBONIYLAR DAVLATI VA USMONLI TURKLAR DAVLATI O'RTASIDAGI DASTLABKI ALOQALAR TAVSIFI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 147–154. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/60142>
22. Rahmonova, S. (2025). IJTIMOIIY BEGONALASHUVNING OLDINI OLISHDA MA'NAVIY-MARIFIY ISLOHOTLARNING O'RNI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 428–435. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/60835>
23. Rahmonova, S., & Yo'ldasheva, M. (2025). TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 367–374. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/63683>
24. I. Gadayeva, M. (2025). PARANJIDAN VOZ KECHILGAN KUN:" YANGI HAYOT" BOSHLANISHI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(5), 771-777.
25. Gadayeva, M. (2025). TARIX DARSLARIDA OQUVCHILARNING BILIM, MALAKA VA KONIKMALARINI HOSIL QILISH VA BAHOLASH. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(5), 792-800.
26. Gadayeva, M. (2025). TARIXIY BILIMLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH JARAYONI VA TARIX DARSLARINING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 1423-1431.
27. Gadayeva, M. (2025). SOMONIYLAR DAVRIDAGI DEVONLAR VA BUGUNGI O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI VAZIRLIKLARINING TAQQOSIY TAHLILI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 381-388.
28. Gadayeva, M. (2025). CHOLPONNING SHERLARIDA ERK, OZODLIK VA OZLIK MASALALARI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 549-563.
29. Gadayeva, M. (2025). ABDULHAMID CHOLPONNING JADIDCHILIK HARAKATIDAGI ORNI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 1013-1019.
30. Gadayeva, M. (2025). TURKISTONLIK GENERAL AYOL, MILLAT ONASI-QURBONJON DODXOHNING MARD, JASUR VA VATANPARVARLIGI HAQIDA. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 344-352.
31. Gadayeva, M. (2024). MARKAZIY OSIYODA JADID AYOLLARI TARIXI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 652-658.
32. Muxamedovna, G. M. (2024). Millatimiz Faxri-Buxoro Ma'rifatparvari. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 52, 557-562.
33. Muxamedovna, G. M. (2024). TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA AXBOROT KOMMUNIKATSIYA TEXNOLOGIYALARINING O 'RNI. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 4(5), 97-102.
34. Mukhamedovna, G. M. (2024). The Sad Fate Of The Women Of Turkistan: About The "Hujum" Movement And Its Impacts On Agriculture. *SPAST Reports*, 1(7).
35. Muxamedovna, G. M. (2023). MAKTABLARDA TARIX FANINI O'QITISH AHAMIYATI. *Научный Фокус*, 1(5), 178-180.
36. Muxamedovna, G. M. (2023). TARIX FANINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI. *Научный Фокус*, 1(5), 175-177.

37. Gadayeva, M. (2024). ABOUT THE HISTORY OF THE VEIL OR MEDIEVAL WOMEN'S DRESS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 1097-1103.
38. Gadayeva, M. (2023). THE UNIQUE SIGNIFICANCE OF MASTERING SOCIAL SCIENCES DURING THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NEW UZBEKISTAN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 459-464.
39. Universiteti, G. M. M. O. X. (2023). Uchinchi Renesans Davrida Ajdodlarimiz Merosini Organish Orqali Integratsion Ta'Limni Yanada Takomillashtirish Tamoyillari: Часть 1 Том 1 Июль 2023 Год. Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования, 1(1), 11-16.
40. Gadayeva, M. (2024). Attack Action. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 1028-1033.
41. Gadayeva, M. (2024). Effective Ways To Use The" Thoughtstorm" Method On The Theme Of The" Eastern Renaissance" Era. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 1024-1027.
42. Muxamedovna, G. M. (2023). KREATIV YONDASHUV ASOSIDA DIDAKTIK MATERIALLAR YARATISH MEKANIZMLARI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 21(3), 12-14.
43. Muxamedovna, G. M. (2023). Uchinchi renesans davrida ajdodlarimiz merosini organish orqali integratsion ta'limni yanada takomillashtirish tamoyillari. Образование наука и инновационные идеи в мире, 22(1), 35-38.
44. Muxamedovna, G. M. (2023). History Of Patriotic Women. *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 3(12), 69-75.
45. Muxamedovna, G. M. (2023). Innovatsion TaLim-Buyuk Kelajak Poydevori. *World scientific research journal*, 17(1), 74-76.
46. Gadayeva, M. (2024). Effective Ways To Use The" Thoughtstorm" Method On The Theme Of The" Eastern Renaissance" Era. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 1024-1027.
47. Gadayeva, M., & Ismoilova, Z. (2024). The Importance Of Studying The Science Of Youth Psychology In Improving People'S Lives. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 676-683.
48. Gadayeva, M., & Hamroqulova, N. (2024). The Basis Of The Use Of Development-Pedagogical Skills In Pedagogical Activity. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 684-689.
49. Gadayeva, M., & Sabriddinova, G. (2025). JADIDLAR FAOLIYATIDA XOTIN-QIZLARNING ORNI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 648-655.
50. Toshpo'latova, S. (2025). BO'LAJAK TARIX O'QITUVCHILARINING PEDAGOGIK-PSIXOLOGIK TAYYORGARLIGINING UMUMIY KONTSEPTSIYASI VA AHAMIYATI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 481-484.
51. Toshpo'latova, S. (2025). FOROBIYNING DIDAKTIK QARASHLARI ASOSIDA O'QUVCHILARNI TARIX FANIGA QIZIQTIRISH METODIKASI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 177-186.
52. Toshpo'latova, S., & Tursunova, S. (2025). TURKISTONDAGI-BIRINCHI DRAMMA. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 468-480.
53. Toshpo'latova, S., Gadayeva, M., & Sadullayev, U. (2024). SHARQ ALLOMALARINING DIDAKTIK QARASHLARI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 985-993.

54. Gadayeva, M., Toshpolatova, S., & Sadullayev, U. (2024). TARIX FANLARINI OQITISHDA MUZEYLARNING ORNI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 994-1003.
55. Sadullayev, U., Gadayeva, M., & Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). MAHALLA-QADRIYATLAR BESHIGI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 1228-1238.
56. Toshpo'latova Shaxnoza Shuhratovna. (2024). ILK UYG'ONISH DAVRI NAMOYONDALARNING DIDAKTIK QARASHLARI ASOSIDA O'QUVCHILARNI TARIX FANIGA QIZIQTIRIS METODIKASI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14520996>
57. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). TARIX FANINI O'QITISHDA SAMARALI METODLAR. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(11), 774-782.
58. Тошполатова, Ш. (2024). THE PRESENT IRANIANS. *Журнал универсальных научных исследований*, 2(5), 453-462.
59. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). BUXORODAGI SAROYLAR. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(5), 522-529.
60. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). O'RTA ASRLARDA OILA PEDAGOGIKASIGA OID FIKRLAR. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 353-361.
61. Toshpo'latova, S., & Xudoyqulov, S. (2024). History And Ethnology Of Olot District. *Modern Science And Research*, 3(5), 148-151.
62. Toshpo'latova, S., & Jo'rayeva, M. (2024). HISTORY AND ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS OF JONDOR DISTRICT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 447-450.
63. Qizi, R. S. S., Shukhratovna, T. S., & Karamatovna, M. A. (2024). Implementation of Education and Protection of Children's Rights in the age of Technology. *SPAST Reports*, 1(7).
64. Shuhratovna, T. S. (2024). Linguistic Anthropology. *European Journal Of Innovation In Nonformal Education*, 4(3), 432-437.
65. Toshpo'latova, S. S., & Naimov, I. N. (2023). MS ANDREYEV-O'RTA OSIYO XALQLARI ETNOGRAFIYASINING YIRIK OLIMI. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(8), 1214-1222.
66. Toshpo'latova, S., & Tursuntoshova, S. (2024). Khoja Abdulkholiq Gijduvani. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 87-93.
67. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). Ethnolinguistics Of Ethnologies Of Bukhara. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 1004-1011.
68. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). Ethnolinguistics. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 500-507.
69. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). Religious Anthropology. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 504-510.
70. Shakhnoza Shuhratovna, T. (2023). MS Andreyev'S Way Of Life. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769)*, 1(10), 655-659.
71. Shuhratovna, T. S. (2023). Ethnological Analysis Of National Costumes And Rituals Of Tajiks In The Works Of MS Andreyev. *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 3(12), 42-47.
72. Toshpo'latova, S. (2023). MS Andreyev-Scientific Career. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(12), 801-807.
73. Shuhratovna, T. S. (2023). Etymology Of Tajik Marriage Ceremony. *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 3(11), 17-23.

74. Toshpo'latova, S., & Ashurova, G. (2023). THE HISTORY AND DESCRIPTION OF THE WORK OF MS ANDREYEV-" ARK BUKHARI". Modern Science and Research, 2(9), 404-409.
75. Toshpo'latova, S. (2023). ETHNOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF CALENDRIAL CALCULATION AND LENGTH MEASUREMENTS OF KHUF VALLEY TAJIKS IN THE RESEARCHES OF MS ANDREYEV. Modern Science and Research, 2(10), 291-299.
76. Toshpo'latova, S. (2023). A STUDY OF THE WEDDING CEREMONY OF THE TAJIKS OF AFGHANISTAN. Modern Science and Research, 2(9), 84-89.
77. Naimov, I., & Toshpo'latova, S. (2023). Marriage Ceremony Of Tajiks In The Work Of Mikhail Stepanovich Andreyev "Tadjiki Dolini Khuf". International Journal of Intellectual Cultural Heritage, 3(1), 12-16.
78. Toshpo'latova, S. S. (2023). Tojiklar Milliy Kiyim-Kechaklari Va "Beshmorak" Marosimining Etnologik Tahlili. Scholar, 1(28), 395-401.
79. Toshpo'latova, S., & Hoshimova, M. (2025). BERUNIY VA UNING DIDAKTIK QARASHLARI. Modern Science and Research, 4(1), 344-351.
80. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). ILK UYG'ONISH DAVRI NAMOYONDALARNING DIDAKTIK QARASHLARI ASOSIDA O'QUVCHILARNI TARIX FANIGA QIZIQTIRISH METODIKASI. Modern Science and Research, 3(12), 643-651.
81. Muyiddinov, B., Toshpo'latova, S., & Gadayeva, M. (2025). TEMURIYLAR DAVRIDA KUTUBXONACHILIK, HUJJATCHILIK VA ISH YURITISHNING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI. Modern Science and Research, 4(2), 97-105.
82. Toshpo'latova, S., Gadayeva, M., & Muyiddinov, B. (2025). BO'LAJAK O'QITUVCHILARNING PEDAGOGIK-PSIXOLOGIK TAYYORGARLIGINI TARKIB TOPTIRISH MODEL. Modern Science and Research, 4(2), 106-116.